

**THE EFFECT OF STORE ATMOSPHERE, SOCIAL MEDIA
MARKETING, AND LIFESTYLE ON PURCHASE DECISIONS
ON CONSUMERS OF THE ALLEYWAY CAFE**

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to explain the effect of store atmosphere, social media marketing and lifestyle on purchase decisions on the consumers of The Alleyway Cafe. The sampling method used is non-probability sampling. The number of samples is 105 respondents. Data collection is carried out by distributing questionnaires to consumers of The Alleyway Cafe. The data analysis technique used is Multiple Linear Regression Analysis with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24.0 for Windows. The results of the study showed that variable of store atmosphere had a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Likewise, social media marketing and lifestyle have positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Therefore, it is important for The Alleyway Cafe to improve store atmosphere, social media marketing and lifestyle to increase customer purchasing decisions.

Keywords: store atmosphere, social media marketing, lifestyle, purchase decisions

1. Introduction

The development of increasingly advanced times has impact on business competition and business in the culinary field underwent many changes. In this era, the company not only facilitate for food and beverage needs, but also needs of socialization such as business meetings, community meetings or just gathering with colleagues or relatives. This makes cafe and restaurant entrepreneurs must understand the needs, desires, and demands of the target market (Putri et al., 2014). In business field, it is important to know how the company can encourage purchasing decisions (Sari, 2016).

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Consumer purchasing decisions to buy a product can arise due to stimuli offered by the company (Wijaya et al., 2018). One of the considerations in making purchasing decisions is store atmosphere (Putri et al., 2014). Store atmosphere is a tacit communication that can show the social class of the products in store, so that can be used as a tool to persuade consumers to make the purchase decision process (An'nisa, 2016). In purchasing decisions, consumers are also influenced by opinions and reviews on social media, so companies try to take the advantage of trends of using social media for their purchasing decisions (Gupta, 2016). Social media has been used as a means of marketing products or what is commonly referred to as social media marketing (Mileva and Fauzi, 2018). The other variables besides store atmosphere and social media marketing that can influence purchasing decisions is lifestyle. Herawaty et al. (2019), stated that lifestyle is part of consumer behavior that influences consumer decision in making purchases.

The phenomenon that exists today is the proliferation of cafes in the city of Denpasar, in this city the existence of cafes began to be taken into account for teenagers. The Alleyway Cafe is one of the cafes in Denpasar and has been officially opened since 2014. This cafe is interesting to be investigated because it has a unique store atmosphere, which raise the concept of "Industrial Wild Garden", The Alleyway Cafe combines the art of simple decoration while maintaining vintage elements and freedom of expression which is suitable to be used as an 'instagramable' photo spot and as a place to hang out or just gather with relatives. This cafe is also very suitable for consumers who need a comfortable place to complete jobs outside the office or college assignments. Currently, cafe consumers rely on behavior towards what is used, visited, and used so that consumers will usually take photos and status updates on various social media as if self-proof 'exists' to the surrounding community and cyberspace (Fauzi et al., 2017). This is certainly an opportunity for companies to take the advantage of the increasing trend of consumers depending on social media for their purchasing decisions.

Purchasing decisions can also arise because of a lifestyle, where the habit of looking for a place to simply relieve fatigue after work and routine has begun to become a lifestyle in the community. Based on the background description, the aim of this study is to explain the effect of store atmosphere, social media marketing, and lifestyle on purchasing decisions.

2. Conceptual Framework and Research Hypothesis

According to Hanaysha (2018), before making a decision, consumers involve several choices and make purchase after the consumer has the desire to meet his needs. In this study, the indicators used to measure purchasing decision variables are as follows: 1) Needs, 2) Decisions about the number of products, 3) Habits, and 4) Consumer satisfaction raises trust in a product. Store atmosphere is an atmosphere that refers to the physical characteristics of the store's exterior and interior, which shape the image and bring in customers (Tansala et al., 2018). Dharma and Kusumadewi (2018) stated that store atmosphere as a tool of communication that has a positive impact if it is interestingly

packaged, but a negative impact if not addressed. In this study, store atmosphere can be measured by: 1) Cleanliness, 2) Layout, 3) Music, 4) Lighting 5) Temperature.

Kristiani and Dharmayanti (2017) stated that social media marketing as a tool offers a unique opportunity to market businesses, products, and services that had not existed for decades ago. Mileva and Fauzi (2018), social media marketing is a form of direct or indirect marketing that is used to build awareness, recognition, memory, and actions for brands, businesses, products, people, or other entities and is carried out using tools from the web social. In this study, the indicators used to measure social media marketing variables are as follows: 1) Content creation, 2) Be active, and 3) Be interesting. According to Ekasari and Hartono (2015), lifestyle is a part of human secondary needs that can change depending on the era or the desire of someone to change their lifestyle, whereas according to Tampanatu et al. (2014) argues that lifestyle is showing how people live, how to spend their money, and how to allocate time. In this study, the indicators used to measure lifestyle variables are as follows: 1) Activities, 2) Interest, and 3) Opinion.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

The results of Fikri and Mulazid's research (2018) showed that store atmosphere significantly effect on consumer's buying decision process. In line with Jaya and Suparna's research (2018), which proves that the store atmosphere has a positive and significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions and Tansala et al. (2019) states that there is a strong influence between store atmosphere and purchasing decisions.

H1: Store atmosphere has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions
The results of Mileva and Fauzi's research (2018), showed that social media marketing has a simultaneous and partial effect on purchasing decisions. Caecilia et al. (2017) states that social media marketing is proven to have a significant effect on purchasing decisions, and in the research of Gupta (2016) also showed that social media has a good influence on consumer purchasing decisions.

H2: Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions

Herawaty et al. (2019) in his research showed that lifestyle has a positive effect on consumer purchasing decisions. Rahmadika and Tatiana's research (2018) states that lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. In line with Khalik and Permatasari's research (2018) which also showed that lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions.

H3: Lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions

3. Material and Methods

This type of research is categorized as a type of associative quantitative research that aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables (Sugiyono, 2017: 20). The relationship between two or more variables in this study discusses the effect of store atmosphere on purchasing decisions, social media marketing on purchasing decisions and lifestyle on purchasing decisions. This research was conducted in the city of Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia. This location was chosen because The Alleyway Cafe is located at Jalan Merdeka No.10B, Sumerta Kelod, East Denpasar District, Denpasar City.

In this study, the target population is all consumers who have visited The Alleyway Cafe. The sampling method used in this study is non probability sampling with a purposive sampling technique that is determining the sample with certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2017: 144). In this study, the criteria of the samples are: 1) Respondents who have visited The Alleyway Cafe, 2) Respondents have an account and are active on social media Instagram and Facebook, 3) With minimum education level at least high school/vocational equivalent. Sugiyono (2014: 129) stated that the number of samples are at least 5-10 times of the number of indicators to be examined. This study uses 15 indicators, so by using estimation based on the number of parameters obtained a sample size 75-150 respondents. Based on these considerations, the sample size of this study was set at 105 respondents.

Data collection methods in this study used are instruments in the form of questionnaires, which distributed directly to respondents. The items used in the questionnaire are measured using five-level Likert scale, categorized as disagree = 1, disagree = 2, quite agree = 3, agree = 4, and definitely agree = 5.

The instruments used are tested for validity and reliability in order to check what they can measure and to know the consistency of the responses given by respondents. The validity test of the instruments used is the Pearson Product Moment correlation technique with a minimum limit of $r = 0.3$. The reliability test of the instruments is conducted by calculating the reliability coefficient of Cronbach's Alpha with a minimum limit of Alpha coefficients > 0.6 . Furthermore, the data will be processed using multiple linear regression analysis techniques using the SPSS 24.00 for windows program.

The analysis model of multiple regression in question is as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Information:

Y = Purchase Decision

α = Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression coefficients of each variable

X1 = Store Atmosphere

X2 = Social Media Marketing

X3 = Lifestyle

ε = Variable Error

4. Results and Discussion

Research respondents are described in general terms by presenting the characteristics seen from demographic variables are gender, age, education and employment. The amount used in this study is 105 respondents.

Table 1: Characteristics of respondents

No	Variable	Classification	Total (person)	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	47	45
		Female	58	55
			105	100
2	Age	17 – 20 years old	15	14
		21 – 25 years old	88	84
		26 – 35 years old	2	2
			105	100
3	Education	Senior High School	73	70
		Diploma	6	6
		Bachelor	23	22
		Magister	3	3
			105	100
4	Employment	Student	84	80
		Government employees	2	2
		Private employees	15	14
		Entrepreneur	3	3
		Etc.	1	1
			105	100

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Table 1 shows that the respondents in this study were dominated by women as many as 55 percent. This is caused by the store atmosphere of The Alleyway Cafe is very suitable as an instagramable photo spot and women are more dominant to take selfies. For classification respondent based on age, the age group of 21-25 years had the highest percentage of 84 percent because at this age, they have a lifestyle for leisure activities and socializing together in cafe. Based on the level of education, high school education dominates in this study at 70 percent. This is because they are easily influenced by social

media when making purchases in cafes and seem to be proof of self that exists to the surrounding community and cyberspace. For the classification of respondents based on employment, in this study were dominated by students as many as 80 percent. This is because students are more dominant requires a clean and comfortable place to finish their task of collage or work, so cafe become one of the alternative places.

The instrument is considered to meet the requirements of the validity test if the correlation coefficient value ≥ 0.3 . The results of the validity tests of each instrument are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: The Results of the Validity Tests

Variable	Indicator	Coefficient Correlation	Information
Store Atmosphere (X1)	Cleanliness	0,932	Valid
	Layout	0,786	Valid
	Music	0,939	Valid
	Lighting	0,864	Valid
	Temperature	0,929	Valid
Social Media Marketing (X2)	Content creation	0,947	Valid
	Be active	0,913	Valid
	Be interesting	0,940	Valid
Lifestyle (X3)	Activities	0,950	Valid
	Interest	0,923	Valid
	Opinion	0,888	Valid
Purchase Decisions (Y)	Needs	0,877	Valid
	Decisions about the number of products	0,971	Valid
	Habits	0,900	Valid
	Consumers satisfaction raises trust in a product	0,846	Valid

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

The validity test results in Table 2 show that each indicator variable has a Pearson correlation value greater than 0.30, means the indicators or questions in the research instrument are valid, so this is appropriate to be used to conduct research.

An instrument can be said to be reliable if the value of Cronbach's alpha is greater than 0.60. The reliability test results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: The Results of The Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
Store Atmosphere (X1)	0,933	Reliable
Social Media Marketing (X2)	0,923	Reliable
Lifestyle (X3)	0,907	Reliable
Purchase decisions (Y)	0,896	Reliable

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Table 3 shows that the entire research instrument had a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient greater than 0.60. This shows that all variables meet the requirements of reliability so that they can be used to conduct research.

Describe the responses of respondents regarding the variables in this study using the following measurement criteria: 1) 1.00-1.79 = very not good / very low; 1.80-2.59 = not good / low; 2.60-3.39 = good enough / high enough; 3.40-4.19 = good / high; 4.20-5.00 = very good / very high.

Store atmosphere in this study is an independent variable that is depicted with the symbol X1 and measured using 5 indicators. Respondents' responses can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Description of Respondents' Responses to Store Atmosphere

Indicator	Answer Score					Total Score	Average	Criteria
	1	2	3	4	5			
Cleanliness	0	0	15	46	44	449	4,28	Very good
Layout	0	0	16	56	33	437	4,16	Good
Music	0	0	21	47	37	436	4,15	Good
Lighting	0	1	20	51	33	431	4,10	Good
Temperature	0	3	22	43	37	429	4,09	Good
Average							4,16	Good

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Based on Table 4 obtained the average value of respondents' responses to the store atmosphere that is equal to 4.16 included in good criteria, this means that respondents responded well to the store atmosphere served by The Alleyway Cafe so that it can stimulate consumers' perceptions and emotional responses that will ultimately improve consumer decisions in making purchases at the cafe.

Social media marketing in this study is an independent variable that is depicted with the symbol X2 and measured using 3 indicators. Respondents' responses can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Description of Respondents' Responses to Social Media Marketing

Indicator	Answer Score					Total Score	Average	Criteria
	1	2	3	4	5			
Content creation	0	3	15	56	31	430	4,10	Good
Be active	0	3	20	43	39	433	4,12	Good
Be interesting	0	5	23	48	29	416	3,96	Good
Average							4,06	Good

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Based on Table 5. obtained a value of 4.06 which is included in good criteria, this means that the management of social media marketing that was designed and conducted by The Alleyway Cafe received a good response from consumers.

Lifestyle in this study is an independent variable illustrated by the X3 symbol and measured using 3 indicators. Respondents' responses can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6: Description of Respondents' Responses to Lifestyle

Indicator	Answer Score					Total Score	Average	Criteria
	1	2	3	4	5			
Activities	0	0	12	40	53	461	4,39	Very good
Interest	0	2	14	49	40	442	4,21	Very good
Opinion	0	1	22	36	46	442	4,21	Very good
Average							4,27	Very good

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Based on Table 6. the average value of respondents' responses to lifestyle is 4.27 which is included in the very good criteria, this means that the respondent gave a positive response to the lifestyle relaxing and socializing with relatives in the cafe.

Purchasing decisions in this study are dependent variables depicted with the Y symbol and measured using 4 indicators. The calculation results in Table 7. show the average respondent's answers about the purchase decision.

Table 7: Description of Respondents' Responses to Purchase Decision

Indicator	Answer Score					Total Score	Average	Criteria
	1	2	3	4	5			
Needs	0	2	13	51	39	442	4,21	Very good
Decisions about the number of products	0	7	19	46	33	420	4,00	Good
Habits	0	2	20	41	42	438	4,17	Good
Consumers satisfaction raises trust in a product	0	0	21	49	35	434	4,13	Good
Average							4,10	Good

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Based on Table 7 obtained an average value of respondents' responses of 4.10 included in the criteria both, this means the decision to make a purchase at the cafe was welcomed and positive by the respondent.

Multiple regression analysis is used to test the effect of store atmosphere, social media marketing, and lifestyle on purchasing decisions. The results of this analysis can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8: Regression Test Results of Store Atmosphere, Social Media Marketing and Lifestyle on Purchase Decisions

Variable	Regression Coefficient		T	Sig
	B	Std. Error		
(constant)	0,198	0,259	0,765	0,446
Store Atmosphere	0,247	0,085	2,902	0,005
Social Media Marketing	0,326	0,072	4,505	0,000
Lifestyle	0,371	0,079	4,710	0,000
Dependent variable	: Purchase decisions			
F Statistic	: 83,813			
Sig. F	: 0,000			
R ²	: 0,713			
Adjusted R ²	: 0,705			

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019

Based on Table 8. can be written multiple linear regression equations as follows.

$$Y = 0.247 X_1 + 0.326 X_2 + 0.371 X_3 + e$$

The multiple linear regression equation can be described as follows: 1). Store atmosphere, social media marketing and lifestyle have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions for consumers at The Alleyway Cafe, and 2). R square value is 0.713, which means that 71.3 percent of variations in purchasing decisions are influenced by store atmosphere, social media marketing, and lifestyle, while the remaining 28.7 percent is influenced by other factors not included in the research model.

The classic assumption test is conducted to test the feasibility of the model that will be created before it is used in predicting. Classic assumption tests include: normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test. The normality test will be shown in Table 9 The results obtained using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with a significance greater than 0.05, namely 0.130, it can be concluded that the regression model is normally distributed.

Table 9: The Results of Normality Test

Unstandardized Residual		
N		105
Normal Parameters (a,b)	Mean	0,0000000
	Std. Deviation	0,33872952
Most Extreme differences	Absolute	0,114
	Positive	0,062
	Negative	-0,114
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1,169
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0,130

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

A regression model is said to be good if it is free of multicollinear symptoms. The presence or absence of this symptom is seen from the value of the variance inflation factor (VIF). If the VIF is less than 10, then it says there is no multicollinearity.

Table 10: The Results of Multicollinearity Test

No.	Variable	Collinearity Statistic	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Store Atmosphere	0,458	2,184
2	Social Media Marketing	0,453	2,209
3	Lifestyle	0,466	2,146

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Based on the test results shown in Table 10, it can be seen that the VIF value of each independent variable is less than 10, namely the store atmosphere variable (X1) has a VIF value of $2.184 < 10$, the social media marketing variable (X2) has a VIF value of $2.209 < 10$,

and lifestyle variables (X3) have a VIF value = 2.146 < 10. These results prove that the regression model in this study did not experience symptoms of multicollinearity.

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is a variance in variance from the residuals of one observation to another. If the significance level of each independent variable is greater than 0.05, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity. Heteroscedasticity test results are shown in Table 11 below:

Table 11: The Results of Heteroscedasticity Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	0,367	0,164		2,240	0,027
Store Atmosphere	-0,093	0,054	-0,248	-1,721	0,088
Social Media Marketing	-0,013	0,046	-0,042	-0,291	0,772
Lifestyle	0,077	0,050	0,221	1,547	0,125

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Based on the test results shown in Table 11, it can be seen that the significance value of each independent variable is above 0.05, namely the store atmosphere variable (X1) has a sig value. = 0.088 > 0.05, the variable social media marketing (X2) has a sig value = 0.772 > 0.05 and the lifestyle variable (X3) has a sig value = 0.125 > 0.05. These results prove that the regression model in this study is free from symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Table 12: The Results of F-Test

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	29,707	3	9,902	83,813	0,000 ^a
Residual	11,933	101	0,118		
Total	41,639	104			

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Based on Table 12 it can be seen that F-count = 83,813 with a significance value of 0,000 < 0.05, it can be concluded that the store atmosphere (X1), social media marketing (X2), and lifestyle (X3) simultaneously affect the purchasing decision (Y) on The Alleyway Cafe consumers.

Table 13: The Results of t-Test

Model	T	Sig.	The results of hypothesis
1 (Constant)	0,765	0,446	
Store Atmosphere	0,2902	0,005	H ₁ accepted
Social Media Marketing	4,505	0,000	H ₁ accepted
Lifestyle	4,710	0,000	H ₁ accepted

Source: Primary data processing results, 2019.

Hypothesis testing (t test) was carried out to test the significance of the influence of the store atmosphere independent variable (X1), social media marketing (X2) and lifestyle (X3) partially on the purchase decision dependent variable (Y). The store atmosphere variable (X1) has t-count = 2.902, the significance value = 0.005 Because the significance result ≤ 0.05 , H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected, this means the store atmosphere has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. The social media marketing variable (X2) has a t-count = 4.505 and a significance value = 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. The test results indicate that H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected, this means that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Lifestyle variable (X3) has a t-count = 4,710 with a significance value = 0,000 less than 0.05 so that H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This means that lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions.

4.1 The effect of store atmosphere on purchasing decisions

The first objective in this study is to explain the effect of store atmosphere on purchasing decision. Based on the results of statistical tests that have been described that there is a positive and significant effect between store atmosphere on purchasing decisions. These results indicate that the better store atmosphere created by The Alleyway Cafe will be able to stimulate consumers' perceptions and emotional responses which in turn will increase consumer decisions in making purchases at the cafe. The results of this study are also supported by research from Tansala et al. (2019), that stated there is a strong influence between store atmosphere and purchasing decisions. Jaya and Suparna (2018) prove that the store atmosphere has a positive and significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions.

4.2 The effect of social media marketing on purchasing decisions

The second objective in this study is to explain the effect of social media marketing on purchasing decisions. The results of this study indicate there is a positive and significant effect between social media marketing on purchasing decision where the better social media marketing is managed and designed by The Alleyway Cafe, it will be able to improve consumer decisions in making purchases at the cafe. This research is supported by research conducted by Mileva and Fauzi (2018), showed that social media marketing has a simultaneous and partial effect on purchasing decisions. In line with Putri's research (2016), it also showed that social media variables significantly effect on purchasing decisions.

4.3 The effect of lifestyle on purchasing decisions

The third objective in this study is to explain the effect of lifestyle on purchasing decisions. Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant effect between lifestyle on purchasing decisions. These results indicate that if the lifestyle has increased it will be able to influence consumer decisions in making purchases at the cafe. This research gets positive results and included in the criteria very

well on the three indicators (activities, interests, and opinions). It means that consumers make purchasing decisions at the cafe influenced by lifestyle in the community. This research is supported by research conducted by Khalik and Permatasari (2018) which shows that lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions and in the research of Wijaya et al. (2018) also states that lifestyle has a significant effect on purchasing decisions.

5. Theoretical Implications

This research has implications for the development of concepts related to store atmosphere, social media marketing, lifestyle and consumer purchasing decisions. This study enriches empirical evidence of the relationship of store atmosphere, social media marketing, lifestyle and purchasing decisions. The results of this study indicate the effect of variables such as the effect of store atmosphere variables on purchasing decisions. The better store atmosphere can improve cozy places, and it can improve consumer decisions in making purchases at the cafe. Furthermore, there is an effect between social media marketing variables on purchasing decisions. This research shows that if social media marketing is well designed, it will affect consumers' decisions when purchasing at a cafe. Then, there is an effect between lifestyle variables on purchasing decisions. If one's lifestyle is getting better or higher, it will be able to make a significant contribution in improving consumer decisions in making purchases at the cafe.

6. Practical Implications

The results of this study have implications for the management of The Alleyway Café, especially for "cleanliness" indicator, that can affect consumer decisions in making purchases at the cafe. Beside of that, consumers make a purchasing decision also influenced by information, comments and feedback from other people and social media marketing, so the café's management must be able to design and manage social media as well so that consumers are aware of the products offered by The Alleyway Cafe, and finally decided to make a purchase. Based on the results of the highest assessment, the indicator "be active" variable social media marketing shows if the social media of The Alleyway is more updated and active, it will affect consumers' decisions in making purchases at the cafe. The relationship between lifestyle and purchasing decisions can provide information to the management of The Alleyway Cafe in segmenting consumers based on the lifestyle adopted so as to be able to get potential consumers to make purchases at The Alleyway Café. Addition, if viewed from the highest ratings, there is an indicator of "activities" indicating that leisure and socializing activities with relatives are very comfortable to do in a cafe so that this can influence consumer purchasing decisions.

7. Conclusions

Based on the research results that have been described, the conclusions obtained are as follows: 1) Store atmosphere has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions on consumers of The Alleyway Cafe. This means that the better the store atmosphere created by The Alleyway Cafe, will be able to stimulate consumers' perceptions and emotional responses that will ultimately effect on consumer purchasing decisions. 2) Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions on consumers of The Alleyway Cafe. This means that the better the social media marketing that is designed it will affect the consumer's decision to make a purchase at The Alleyway Cafe. 3) Lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions on consumers of The Alleyway Cafe. This means that the lifestyle adopted by a person will influence consumer decisions in making purchases at The Alleyway Cafe.

8. Suggestions

Based on the conclusions that have been outlined, the following suggestions can be put forward: 1) The lowest assessment result on the store atmosphere variable is in the indicator "temperature" then the management of The Alleyway Cafe should manage the temperature in the cafe better so that it can create a comfortable store atmosphere so that it is compelled to make a purchasing decision at The Alleyway Cafe. 2) The lowest rating results are in the indicator "be interesting" then the management of The Alleyway Cafe should create more innovative content on social media so that it can attract the attention of consumers, besides that the topic raised on any content should be more varied such as promos, discounts or procurement of giveaway on certain events. 3) The lowest assessment results on lifestyle variables are in the indicator "interest" and on the indicator "opinion" where the management should be more pay attention to lifestyle adopted by someone so that it can attract consumers to make purchases at the cafe, and 4) The lowest valuation result on the purchase decision variable is in the indicator "Decisions about the number of products" where management should review the factors that influence the product maybe in terms of price or quality offered, so the decision consumer purchases can be increased.

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